

TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY DUBLIN

POLICY TO ADDRESS GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

NATIONAL CONTEXT

The issues surrounding gender-based violence (GBV) in Ireland have been outlined in the Second National Strategy on Domestic, Sexual and Gender-Based Violence 2016-2021 and the National Strategy for Women and Girls 2017. Within the higher education sector, the statutory planning and development body for higher education, the Higher Education Authority (HEA), together with direction from the state developed and launched a National Framework in 2019, Safe, Respectful, Supportive and Positive: Ending Sexual Violence and Harassment in Irish Higher Education Institutions Framework. It is a roadmap and toolkit of strategies and policies to be embedded in the duty of care for students and staff in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and research organisations (DES, 2019). Funding was provided to HEIs to support the creation of institutional policies and strategies to implement the National Framework. As a follow-up, on 4 August 2020, Simon Harris, Minister for Further Education and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Science, issued a directive to all HEIs to develop and publish, on their institutional websites, by February 2021, a specific institutional action plan, on tackling sexual violence and harassment within their institution. In order to measure the prevalence of GBV in Irish HEIs Minister Harris announced the launch of a National Staff and Student Survey on Sexual Violence and Sexual Harassment in Higher Education Institutions. This survey was conducted by the HEA in April 2021. It was sent to the entire higher education staff and student population of 39,000 staff and 235,000 students in order to create a robust evidence base for further policy decisions. Each HEI will receive their individual results.

The Irish Universities Association (IUA) created policy Guidance for universities advising that institutional arrangements should be situated within a broader institutional context that focuses on prevention, support, and an institutional culture that promotes the values of respect, dignity, and integrity (IUA, 2019).

INSTITUTIONAL POLICY

In response to the national imperative to end GBV in Irish HEIs, the Technological University Dublin (TUD) responded in the following ways:

- Working Group created to implement the National Framework 2019.
 - Created the *Institutional Action Plan to End Sexual Violence and Harassment 2020*.
- TUD Equality Statement 2021-2022
 - Emphasising TUD's commitment to advancing equality, diversity and inclusion.
- TUD *Policy of Sexual Harassment & Bullying of Students*: updated 8 March 2021. Dissemination of the policy has been slow, with a more focused approach for 2021.
- TUD *Staff Protection, Dignity at Work Policy*: updated May 2021.
- TUD *Gender Identity & Gender Expression Policy for Staff & Students 2020*. Reviewed every 4 years.
- TUD Student Union: Smart Consent / Workshops / IBSA (Image Based Sexual Abuse) Workshops.

This is a set of GBV-focused policies and broader policies addressing the issue as one of its parts.

URLs

- › Ending Sexual Violence and Harassment at TU Dublin - Action Plan 2021-2024: <https://www.tudublin.ie/media/intranet/equality-and-diversity/documents/TU-Dublin-ESVH-ActionPlan-2021-24-FINAL-30-03-21.pdf>
- › Policy on Sexual Harassment & Bullying of Students in the Institute: [https://www.tudublin.ie/media/website/for-students/documents/Policy-on-sexual-harassment-and-bullying-of-students-in-the-Institute-\(3SS05\).docx](https://www.tudublin.ie/media/website/for-students/documents/Policy-on-sexual-harassment-and-bullying-of-students-in-the-Institute-(3SS05).docx)
- › Dignity and Respect at Work: <https://www.tudublin.ie/media/intranet/equality-and-diversity/documents/Dignity-and-Respect-at-Work-HRP003-May-2021.pdf>
- › Gender Identity and Gender Expression Policy: Staff and Students: <https://www.tudublin.ie/media/website/explore/about-the-university/equality-and-diversity/documents/TUDublin-Gender-Identity-and-Gender-Expression-Policy.pdf>

Entry into force:

- Ending Sexual Violence and Harassment at TU Dublin – Action Plan 2021 – 2024: 2021
- Policy on Sexual Harassment & Bullying of Students in the Institute: 2001
- Dignity and Respect at Work: 2019
- Gender Identity and Gender Expression Policy: Staff and Students: 2019.

TRAINING

Ending Sexual Violence and Harassment at TU Dublin – Action Plan 2021 – 2024: As part of the **Institutional Action Plan**, the university's EDI department has focused on rolling out the Active Consent Programme to all staff and students on a voluntary basis. The programme is being offered online presently; participation has yet to be assessed. Active Consent is an initiative researched and developed by NUIG as a toolkit that includes workshops and online engagement to close the

gaps in students' understanding of sexual violence and harassment, including the legal definition of rape, sexual assault, and sexual harassment, and how to access support services. It is a practical resource to be accessed by staff and administrations, including managers and academic and support staff; student representatives working with students' unions, societies and sports clubs or on behalf of their academic disciplines; and the wider community to include internal and external stakeholders such as rape crisis movement, health care providers, and advocacy groups.

The Bystander Intervention Programme at TUD considers all levels of diversity and inclusion and calls out all negative behaviours of a sexual nature, racism, inequality, and harassment. The Bystander Intervention Programme was developed for Irish HEIs by University College Cork (UCC, 2019) as a strategic response to the issues of sexual misconduct and violence among student populations and has led to attitude and behavioural changes across the university among students and staff alike.

Targeted initiatives include: online training programmes and workshops, including Bystander Intervention; workshops/classes provided to all incoming first-year students on consent, bystander training, and allyship; incorporating intercultural awareness of respectful behaviours and expectations into the provision and delivery of classes; workshops/classes provided to all other undergraduate and post-graduate students, including exchange students, on consent, bystander training, and allyship; training and workshops for all staff on the Consent Framework, including reporting, how to take/make disclosures, consent (and definitions of consent), and first response training. In addition to these training plans, TUD will develop an education plan to ensure that all staff and relevant students have the ability to support other staff members and students. No budgets are mentioned. The responsible parties are the Working Group with Staff Training and Development/Student Services, Student Services / Counselling.

Gender Identity and Gender Expression Policy: Staff and Students: All Managers: To ensure training in relation to gender identity and expression is prioritised and is provided with a team-based approach as appropriate.

ROLE IN KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION

Not specified in the institutional report.

CONTENT OF THE POLICY

Forms of gender-based violence: The four policies combined address **five** forms of GBV: sexual violence, sexual harassment, gender-based harassment, online violence and other (gender-based bullying).

The two policies that are GBV-focused (*Ending Sexual Violence and Harassment at TU Dublin - Action Plan 2021 – 2024* and *Policy on Sexual Harassment & Bullying of Students in the Institute*) refer to sexual violence and sexual harassment, including their online forms.

The other two policies, which are not GBV-focused, refer to sexual harassment, gender harassment, and gender-based bullying, including their online forms.

- Gender-Based Violence
- Economic and Financial Violence
- Physical Violence
- Stalking
- Psychological Violence
- Organisational Violence
- Sexual Violence
- Online Violence
- Sexual Harassment
- Other
- Gender-Based Harassment

7Ps covered: The four policies combined cover all **7Ps** – prevalence, prevention, protection, prosecution, provision of services, partnerships and policies.

The most commonly tackled Ps are prevention and protection (all four policies). Prosecution, provision of services, and partnership are included in three policies.

UniSAFE has developed the 7P model as a basis for analysing policies on GBV. For more information, see the deliverable report D3.1 Report on the conceptual and theoretical state of the art: <https://unisafe-gbv.eu/project-public-deliverables/>

The P for policy is considered in place if the institution has a GBV-focused policy or more general policies that have a procedure for reporting and investigating.

Target groups

Ending Sexual Violence and Harassment at TU Dublin - Action Plan 2021 – 2024

Policy on Sexual Harassment & Bullying of Students in the Institute

Dignity and Respect at Work

Gender Identity and Gender Expression Policy: Staff and Students

All policies target **academic and non-academic staff**. Most of them, except for the Dignity and Respect at Work, also target **students**. The Gender Identity and Gender Expression Policy: Staff and Students also applies to **other** groups such as applicants for employment, former employees, student applicants, alumni, and student union officers, service users, third-party contractors, visitors, customers, and clients of the university.

Specific vulnerable groups: The policies cover **seven** vulnerable groups in total. These are: staff and students with disabilities, staff and students with migrant and ethnic minority backgrounds, LGBTQIA+ staff, and students and other groups.

The Ending Sexual Violence and Harassment at TU Dublin - Action Plan 2021 – 2024 covers six of the above-mentioned groups.

The Gender Identity and Gender Expression Policy: Staff and Students covers LGBTQIA+ staff and students and other groups (all applicants for employment, employees and former employees; all student applicants, students, alumni, and student union officers; all service users, third-party contractors, visitors, customers, and clients of the university). At TU Dublin the aim is to create a supportive and inclusive environment in which all gender identities are welcome and transphobic behaviour and bullying is never tolerated.

Dignity and Respect at Work also covers other groups. The policy deals with complaints against members of staff or by members of staff that include work-associated events such as meetings, conferences, and work-related social events, whether on TU Dublin premises or off site. This includes employees of other organisations, customers, business contacts, or students.

Intersectionality addressed: Yes. The Gender Identity and Gender Expression Policy: Staff and Students addresses intersectionality as part of ensuring that gender minority groups have access to equal treatment in employment and education. It is not specified which intersectional perspectives gender intersects with, it applies to all students, staff, and those engaging with the university.

Bystanders addressed: Yes. The Ending Sexual Violence and Harassment at TU Dublin – Action Plan 2021 – 2024 addresses the issue of bystanders via the Bystander Intervention Training for Staff and Students, implemented and rolled out to all staff and students.

The Gender Identity and Gender Expression Policy: Staff and Students: As part the responsibilities of staff, managers, and supervisors, staff should confidentially inform a manager or supervisor if they are concerned that a colleague is being bullied, harassed, and / or sexually harassed.

Role of perpetrators addressed: Yes. The Policy on Sexual Harassment & Bullying of Students in the Institute specifies that in any investigation, the alleged offender shall be entitled to the same rights as are applicable in the disciplinary procedure. If, as a result of the investigation, the complaint is proved valid, the harasser will be subject to disciplinary action as outlined in the institute's disciplinary procedure. In the case of serious offences, this may include dismissal or expulsion. The Dignity and Respect at Work policy states that offending staff members may be subject to disciplinary procedures up to and including dismissal.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POLICY

Indicators: Yes. The Ending Sexual Violence and Harassment at TU Dublin – Action Plan 2021 – 2024 developed indicators relating to prevalence, prevention, protection, provision of services, partnership, policies:

- Prevalence: Success Indicator – There is an Online Report and Support Tool in place for students and staff to report incidents, and there is ownership of response, reporting and

review actions in place in relation to policies that explicitly address sexual harassment, assault, and consent, and an annual report is provided to the Governing Body.

- **Prevention: Success Indicator** – 100% of incoming, undergraduate, post-graduate students are offered training on consent and on skills for speaking up and calling out unacceptable behaviour; 100% of staff are offered training on consent/harassment/sexual misconduct reporting, policies, and procedures.
- **Protection Success Indicator** – Evidence of awareness campaigns, training, workshops, etc., including a schedule of activities to cover the full academic year, incorporating website links and details (type and duration) of training included in the annual report to the Governing Body.
- **Provision of Services: Success Indicator** – Counselling resources are in place for students and staff along with a Report and Support online service.
- **Partnership: Success Indicator** – Engagement with external specialist agencies (i.e. rape crisis centres, RCNI etc.) is a regular feature of ESVH implementation.
- **Policies: Success Indicator** – A working group is established with appropriate representation and membership and policies that explicitly address sexual harassment, assault, and consent are in place and published online.

The Gender Identity and Gender Expression Policy: Staff and Students has an indicator relating to policies. This policy will be reviewed periodically and at least every 4 years to reflect legal standards, government policy, and practice. The EDI director will inform the University Executive, the EDI Committee, and the Governing Body on any issues or updates to this policy and its implementation.

Monitoring: Yes. The Ending Sexual Violence and Harassment at TU Dublin – Action Plan 2021 – 2024 monitors the number of cases, results of the institutional procedure (the Report & Support Online reporting tool automatically records statistics on sexual violence and harassment, and an annual report on these statistics and on the success of institutional initiatives will be presented to the Governing Authority and the HEA).

The Dignity and Respect at Work policy compiles data for statistical and management information purposes. The senior HR manager on the relevant campus will securely retain material relating to Dignity and Respect at Work, which may be anonymised to be used for compiling statistical and management information purposes. This material may also be used to monitor the operation of this policy and any modifications which may be required.

Evaluation: Yes. The Ending Sexual Violence and Harassment at TU Dublin – Action Plan 2021 – 2024 policy is evaluated annually in line with national policy guidelines and is presented to the Governing Body and to the HEA in order to record compliance.

The Gender Identity and Gender Expression Policy: Staff and Students will be reviewed periodically and at least every 4 years to reflect legal standards, government policy, and practice. The EDI director will inform the University Executive, the EDI Committee, and Governing Body of any issues or updates to this policy and its implementation.

INSTITUTIONAL PROCEDURE

Two policies set out step-by-step procedures for reporting and investigation.

The Policy on Sexual Harassment & Bullying of Students

The policy defines: who to contact, how to report, the investigation procedure, and responsible persons.

This policy is aimed at informing students of the process of reporting sexual harassment and bullying and to inform staff of the procedures that students may use. It outlines the reporting procedure. It does not highlight support for victims or respondents.

Procedure Stages

Who to contact: Before making a formal complaint, a student who feels subjected to harassment is advised to consult one of the contact persons appointed by the president to advise on alleged incidents of harassment in an informal way. Consultation with a contact person is strictly confidential and no further action will be taken without the consent of the complainant.

How to report: If a direct approach to the alleged harasser fails to halt the harassment, or is not appropriate, the person should report the alleged act to a senior member of staff, as detailed above. The person may formally request an interview with the senior member of staff. This meeting will normally be arranged within five days from receipt of the request.

If the alleged harassment is of a serious nature, a contact person will assist the complainant to make a formal complaint. Formal complaints of harassment should be made in writing to the Registrar of the Institute. Formal complaints so made should include the identity of the offender(s) and the general nature of the complaint.

Responsible persons: Complaints should be addressed to: Registrar, Institute of Technology, Blanchardstown, Dublin 15, marking the envelope as 'Confidential'. A reply will be issued to written complaints within five working days.

Description of the investigation: The Registrar will appoint a senior member of the institute to deal with each formal complaint of harassment. This person will deal with the matter with the minimum of delay and will maintain the maximum possible degree of confidentiality throughout the procedure. The principles of natural justice will apply and the rights of both the complainant and of the alleged harasser will be given due regard. Malicious or frivolous complaints may result in disciplinary action against the complainant.

The president will arrange to meet the complainant, in the presence of a colleague, if desired. This will normally occur within five working days of receipt of notification, no later than ten working days after the meeting, the complainant will be advised in writing of the president's response to the complaint. This may include a request for further information, the acceptance or rejection of the grievances, or to call a further meeting, which will be arranged as soon as possible.

If the complainant feels that the complaint has not been dealt with in a satisfactory way, the senior member of staff should be informed. They will then refer the matter to the president for consideration.

Appeals Procedure

A student against whom a complaint of harassment is substantiated has the right to appeal to the Governing Body. Should a person wish to appeal against the president's decision, they should notify the president in writing within ten working days of receipt of the notification of that decision. The president will then make a request to the chair of the Governing Body to set up a panel (Reference 3SS09).

The chair of the Governing Body shall determine the date when the panel will meet to consider a report from the president. The panel shall consist of three members of the Governing Body but will not include any staff or student representatives or the president.

The panel will meet within twenty working days and will be responsible for making a final decision about the grievance.

As soon as possible and in any case no later than ten working days after the meeting, the complainant will be advised in writing of the response to the complaint.

The Dignity and Respect at Work

The policy defines: who to contact, how to report, the investigation procedure, timeframe, and responsible persons.

This document addresses the issue of staff protection, in accordance with national legislation.

The document outlines staff protection under two routes – an informal one and a formal one, which can also contain mediation. As this is a document outlining staff protection policy: the process is very detailed. This is a broad outline of the procedures:

Informal procedure

‘In many instances, complaints of bullying, harassment, and/or sexual harassment can be dealt with successfully on an informal basis. Often such incidents can be resolved amicably between the parties using an informal approach. In many instances, such an intervention should be sufficient to enable the respondent to see the offending behaviour from the complainant’s perspective and no further action may be required. A staff member who feels subjected to bullying, harassment, and/or sexual harassment should take the following actions:

If you feel able, speak privately to the person you feel is bullying, harassing and/or sexually harassing you and make it clear that their behaviour is unacceptable and ask them to stop. If you find it difficult or embarrassing to communicate directly with the person, you may request your line manager or, if preferred another manager/supervisor, a nominated trade union representative or a colleague to speak to the person on your behalf.

Approach a manager/supervisor, any of the Dignity and Respect Contact Colleagues, Trade Union representative or the EAP for advice and guidance on this policy.

Privately record all incidents of bullying, harassment and/or sexual harassment in writing, including time, date and place. It may be of assistance to include a description of your feelings at the time.

Ascertain if there were any witnesses to the behaviour

If possible, avoid situations where you may be alone with the alleged respondent.’

Mediation

‘For the purpose of this policy, mediation is carried out by a neutral, impartial and suitably qualified external mediator who will be appointed by the senior HR manager on the relevant campus. Mediation is a voluntary and independent process which cannot be imposed on parties. It is expected that both parties will reasonably consider mediation as an option to resolve the complaint.’

Formal investigation

How to report: A complainant who wishes to make a complaint against a member of staff, student, or member of the public interacting with staff in the university, and to have it formally investigated, must make their complaint to the senior HR manager on the relevant campus by way of a Formal Complaint Form.

Who to contact: Where the complaint is against the senior HR manager on the relevant campus, that complaint should be submitted to the most senior HR manager in TU Dublin. Where the complaint is against the most senior HR manager in TU Dublin, the complaint should be submitted to the president.

Preliminary Screening: Preliminary Screening is a process for deciding if the alleged behaviour, which is the subject of the complaint and has not been resolved through mediation or informal means, falls within the definition of bullying, harassment, and/or sexual harassment. The rationale for Preliminary Screening is that some complaints of bullying, harassment, and/or sexual harassment may not meet the requirements of the definitions.

Description of the investigation: What follows is a series of:

- Formal Investigation Preparations.
- Formal Investigation Procedure.
- Complainant's Interview.
- Respondents Preparation and Interview.
- Interviews with 'others' and Re-interviews.
- Appeals Procedure.

Page 23 of the policy:

This document reflects the situation as of January 2022.

Acknowledgment: *this vignette has been created on the basis of the work carried out by national researcher Nadine Shinkwin in 2021, as part of the deliverable report D5.1 Inventory of policies and measures to respond to GBV in European universities and research organisations (2022). Available here: https://zenodo.org/record/5939082#.YfvXE_jTW5c*

